

Finite Decision Theory Models, λ -Lipschitz Continuity, and the Failure of Savage's Independence Principle

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Abstract

We discuss the empirical issues of Savage's independence axiom. Afterwards, we prove that his representation theorem can be restored up to a margin of error after supplanting the independence axiom with the axiom we call λ -Lipschitz continuity. Finally, we discuss the philosophical implications and justification of λ -Lipschitz continuity.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation and History of Decision Theory

Undoubtedly, decisions are an integral part of our lives. Popular knowledge states we make upwards of 35,000 of them a day [7, 9]. Rationally, if we can optimise our decisions we can improve our

lives—regardless of how we define “better”. Sometimes, the optimal decision is obvious—a driver stops a car in order to avoid hitting a pedestrian and to prevent car damage which would cost them a large sum of money and endow a great deal of inconvenience upon all parties. Unfortunately, the vast majority of decisions we encounter are not so simple. Decision theory aims to equip us with the framework and tools to make these difficult decisions easier.

The first study of decisions under uncertainty is thought to begin with the correspondence of Pascal and Fermat [6] and Huygens’ treatise on probability [4] in the 17th century. In 1738, D. Bernoulli introduced the notion of expected utility [2]. The first rigorous axiomatisation of decision theory comes from von Neumann and Morgenstern’s 1944 *Theory of Games and Economic Behavior* [5]. Most important to us, in 1954, Savage’s *The Foundations of Statistics* formulated a new set of axioms which generalised von Neumann-Morgenstern’s contexts to contexts where objective probabilities are unavailable [8]. From the late 20th century onwards, decision theory has become a staple of modern theoretical economics and policy.

1.2 Savage’s Independence Principle

One axiom Savage proposed was his independence axiom, or the sure-thing principle (we list it formally as Axiom 2). Informally, it states that if we would choose action f over action g in the case that some event E occurs, and also in the case that E doesn’t occur, then we should choose f over g even if we don’t know whether E occurs. Savage justifies his axiom through a story in which a businessman contemplating a property purchase whose attractiveness depends on the outcome of a presidential election. He asks himself if he would buy the property if the Republican candidate wins, to which he responds yes. He then asks himself if he would buy the property if the Democratic candidate wins, to which he responds yes as well. Thus, he concludes he should buy the property without knowing the election result.

However, there have been several empirical violations of Savage’s independence axiom. In 1992, Tversky and Shafir performed their “two-stage gamble” experiment, where subjects first play a game with binary outcomes (win or lose). When participants had been told the outcome, they were willing to play again, regardless if they had won or lost. However, when participants were not told the outcome, a majority refused to play again—despite being willing in both known cases [10]. In a more technical experiment, Allais presented his namesake paradox in 1953, where he conducted an experiment where he presented pairs of lotteries (eg. (1A v. 1B) and (2A v. 2B)) such that the sure-thing principle requires consistency between them. However, many people chose 1A over 1B, but 2B over 2A [1]. Birnbaum came to the same conclusion in 2004 [3].

That being said, the sure-thing principle plays a key role in Savage’s “crowning glory” of decision theory, his representation theorem. His theorem states that if our preferences over uncertain actions satisfy a number of axioms (the independence-axiom being one of them), then we must rationally act as if we are maximising expected utility. However, we will show that we can recover his representation theorem—up to a degree of error—by replacing the sure-thing principle with another axiom, λ -Lipschitz continuity, when there are finite states and consequences.

2 Preliminaries

The experienced reader may wish to skip this section and go directly to Section 3.

2.1 Prerequisites

The reader should understand basic set theory (subsets, element of, unions, etc.) and formal logic (logical or, logical and, implication, etc.). When we say “or”, we mean the inclusive variant. Firstly, we introduce some notation which might be unfamiliar to some readers. When we write $f : A \rightarrow B$, we are saying that f is a function whose domain is A and co-domain is B . Recall a function must map every

element in the domain to a unique element in the co-domain. We write the *Cartesian product* of A and B as

$$A \times B := \{(a, b) : a \in A, b \in B\}.$$

2.2 Probability

We only need to know a single topic: a finite additive probability measure. Formally, a finitely additive probability measure p on a set S (which is finite in our case) is a function

$$p : \mathcal{P}(S) \rightarrow [0, 1].$$

Here $\mathcal{P}(S)$ is the power set of S (the set of all subsets of S). The measure p must satisfy

1. Non-negativity: for every subset $E \subseteq S$,

$$p(E) \geq 0.$$

2. Normalisation:

$$p(S) = 1.$$

3. Finite additivity: whenever $E, F \subseteq S$ are disjoint,

$$p(E \cup F) = p(E) + p(F).$$

2.3 Inequalities

We use two concepts from elementary real analysis, the max function and the triangle inequality. Let $f : A \rightarrow B$ be a function. Let $S \subseteq A$. When we say $\max_{s \in S} \{f(s)\}$, we mean the maximum value which $f(s)$ attains when $s \in S$. Typically, we would need to prove that this maximum value exists, but since we are working with finite sets, we are ensured it does. The most general form of the triangle inequality states, for a sequence of n terms, with the k th term denoted a_k ,

$$\left| \sum_{k=1}^n a_k \right| \leq \sum_{k=1}^n |a_k|.$$

2.4 Savage's Decision Theory Model

Now we can develop the framework of decision theory. We adopt the formal model used by Savage in [8]. We'll first go over an intuitive explanation of the model and then give a rigorous treatment.

We have a set of possible, mutually exclusive *states*, which will be all the different states of which actions can occur in. We also have a set of mutually exclusive *consequences* which are the result of an action on a state. To tie them all together, we'll have *actions* which, depending on the state, map to a consequence. Finally, we have a *preference relation* on the set of acts, which means we can judge which actions we prefer. As we'll see, this preference relation will follow seven axioms proposed by Savage.

Formally, let a decision model $\mathcal{M} := (S, X, F)$ be a triplet of state set S , consequence set X , and action set $F \subseteq S \times X$ —that is, if $f \in F$, then $f : S \rightarrow X$. We assume S and X are finite. Finally, there exists a preference relation \succeq which is a subset of $F \times F$. We explicitly note the strong \succ , defined as, for $f, g \in F$,

$$f \succ g \iff (f \succeq g) \wedge (g \not\succeq f).$$

Savage proposed the following seven axioms.

Axiom 1 (Ordering) *The preference relation \succeq is complete and transitive. That is, for any acts $f, g, h \in F$,*

1. (Completeness). *Either $f \succeq g$ or $g \succeq f$.*

2. (Transitivity). If $f \succeq g$ and $g \succeq h$, then $f \succeq h$.

Intuitively, this means that we can prefer any actions in F . Moreover, if we prefer f to g and g to h , we should prefer f to h .

Axiom 2 (Independence Axiom) Let $f, g \in F$ be acts and $E \subseteq S$ be an event. Define

$$f_E g(s) := \begin{cases} f(s) & s \in E \\ g(s) & s \notin E. \end{cases}$$

The axiom states for any event $E \subseteq S$ and acts $f, g, h, h' \in F$,

$$f_E h \succeq g_E h \implies f_E h' \succeq g_E h'.$$

The independence axiom states that our preference between acts f and g shouldn't depend on what happens off E . The main focus of this paper is to investigate what occurs when this axiom is replaced.

Axiom 3 (Monotonicity in Consequences) Let $x, y \in X$ be consequences. Define the constant acts $f(s) := x$ and $g(s) := y$ for all $s \in S$. Then for every non-empty event $E \subseteq S$,

$$f \succeq g \iff f_E h \succeq g_E h,$$

for all $h \in F$.

This axiom states that the ranking of consequences agrees with their state-conditional rankings.

Axiom 4 (Independence of Beliefs from Tastes) For any events $E, E' \subseteq S$ and constant acts $f \succ g$ and $f' \succ g'$ (defined similarly to the previous axiom 3),

$$f_E g \succeq f_{E'} g \iff f'_E g' \succeq f_{E'} g'.$$

This means that our judgement of how likely one event (E) is compared to another (E') shouldn't depend on the value of the payoffs.

Axiom 5 (Non-Triviality) There exists acts $f, f' \in F$ such that $f \succ f'$.

Non-triviality just rules out the degenerate case where we would be indifferent to any action.

Axiom 6 (Event-Continuity) If $f \succ g$, for $f, g \in F$, then for any act h there is a finite partition $\pi := \{E_1, E_2 \dots E_n\}$ of S such that for every $1 \leq i \leq n$,

$$f \succ g_{E_i} h \quad \text{and} \quad h_{E_i} f \succ g.$$

Event-continuity means that we can always partition the state set into fine enough subsets so that we don't reverse the inequality. Savage proposed a seventh axiom, which is important when X is infinite. However, since we are working with finite S and X , we don't need to concern ourselves with it.

3 Setup

Let $\mathcal{M} := (S, X, F)$ along with the binary relation \succeq (and \succ), be a finite decision theory model with $|S| = n$, adhering to all the axioms presented in Section 2.4. Savage, building on von-Neumann and Morgenstern's seminal representation theorem—which they presented in [5]—developed his own representation theorem to work with his decision framework. Here we present the theorem for the finite case.

Theorem 1 (Savage's Representation Theorem) *Let $f, g \in F$ be acts. Then there exists a function $U : F \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that*

$$f \succeq g \iff U(f) \geq U(g).$$

Moreover,

$$U(f) := \sum_{s \in S} u(f(s))p(s),$$

where p is a finitely additive probability measure on S , and $u : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a function.

The representation theorem means we are able to represent preferences as an expected-utility equation. We now modify Savage's framework by replacing Axiom 2 with a new axiom. Before we do, we first define U and u to completely become independent of Axiom 2 and the representation theorem. We may do this by virtue of F 's finite nature. Define $u : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as any function such that

$$\kappa_x \succeq \kappa_y \iff u(x) \geq u(y),$$

where $\kappa_x, \kappa_y : S \rightarrow X$ are the constant functions resulting in consequences x and y respectively. let \bar{x} and \underline{x} be the elements which satisfy

$$\kappa_{\bar{x}} \succeq \kappa_x \quad \text{and} \quad \kappa_x \succeq \kappa_{\underline{x}}$$

for all $x \in X$. Normalise u such that $u(\underline{x}) = 0$ and $u(\bar{x}) = M := \max_{x \in X} \{u(x)\}$. Again, since F is finite, there exists some function $U : F \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ which adheres to

$$f \succeq g \iff U(f) \geq U(g).$$

Likewise, normalise U such that $U(\kappa_{\underline{x}}) = 0$ and $U(\kappa_{\bar{x}}) = M$. Hence we have established u and U without any of the axioms. We may now proceed to defining λ -Lipschitz Continuity.

4 λ -Lipschitz Continuity

We first state the axiom, then construct p and V , and finally prove Theorem 2.

4.1 Axiom and Representation Theorem

Replace Axiom 2 (independence) with the following.

Axiom 7 (λ -Lipschitz Continuity) *Let $f, g, h \in F$ be acts. Let $E \subseteq S$ be a singleton event. If*

$$f_E h = g_E h,$$

then

$$|U(f) - U(g)| \leq \lambda \max_{s, t \in S} \{|u(f(s)) - u(g(t))|\},$$

where $\lambda > 0$ is a real number. Note that if $E = \{e\}$, $\max_{s, t \in S} \{|u(f(s)) - u(g(t))|\} = |u(f(e)) - u(g(e))|$, since e is the only state f and g differ in.

We will discuss the philosophical implications of this axiom in the next section. Note that if $\lambda = 0$, we would be indifferent to all events, contradicting Axiom 5 (Non-Triviality). Our main result is showing we can restore the representation theorem to a certain degree of accuracy. To wit, we prove the following theorem.

Theorem 2 (Savage's Representation Theorem For λ -Lipschitz Continuity) *Let f be an act. Then there exists a function $V : F \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that*

$$|U(f) - V(f)| \leq 2\lambda|S|M = 2\lambda nM,$$

where

$$V(f) := \sum_{s \in S} p(s)u(f(s)).$$

Here, p is a almost-finitely additive probability measure on S .

Almost-finitely additive means if $E, F \subseteq S$ are disjoint,

$$|p(E \cup F) - p(E) - p(F)| \leq \lambda \mathcal{O}(|E|, |F|),$$

where \mathcal{O} is a function which depends only on the cardinality of E and F . We will first prove the existence of V , then show that p is an almost-finitely additive probability measure on S .

4.2 Construction of Probability Measure and Expected Utility

Define $p : S \rightarrow [0, 1]$ as

$$p(s) := \frac{U(\delta_s)}{M},$$

where

$$\delta_s(t) := \begin{cases} \bar{x} & t = s \\ \underline{x} & t \neq s \end{cases}$$

and $s \in S$. Also generalise δ_E for subset $E \subseteq S$. Define $V : F \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as

$$V(f) := \sum_{s \in S} p(s)u(f(s)).$$

4.3 Telescoping Equalities

Let f be an act. We can interpolate between f and $\kappa_{\underline{x}}$ with a sequence of acts. Define

$$f^{(0)} := \kappa_{\underline{x}}, \quad f^{(k)}(s) := \begin{cases} f(s) & s \in \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_k\} \\ \underline{x} & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad f^{(n)} = f.$$

Recognise that the sum $(U(f^{(1)}) - U(f^{(0)})) + (U(f^{(2)}) - U(f^{(1)})) + \dots + (U(f^{(n)}) - U(f^{(n-1)}))$ telescopes:

$$U(f) - U(\kappa_{\underline{x}}) = U(f^{(n)}) - U(f^{(0)}) = \sum_{k=1}^n (U(f^{(k)}) - U(f^{(k-1)})).$$

Likewise,

$$V(f) - V(\kappa_{\underline{x}}) = \sum_{k=1}^n (V(f^{(k)}) - V(f^{(k-1)})).$$

Moreover, since we have

$$\begin{aligned}
V(f^{(k)}) - V(f^{(k-1)}) &= \sum_{j=1}^n p(s_j)u(f^{(k)}(s_j)) - \sum_{j=1}^n p(s_j)u(f^{(k-1)}(s_j)) \\
&= \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} p(s_j)(u(f^{(k)}(s_j)) - u(f^{(k-1)}(s_j))) + \sum_{j=k}^n p(s_j)u(f^{(k)}(s_j)) - \sum_{j=k}^n p(s_j)u(f^{(k-1)}(s_j)) \\
&= \underbrace{\sum_{j=1}^{k-1} p(s_j)(u(f(s_j)) - u(f(s_j)))}_{=\sum_{j=1}^{k-1} p(s_j)(0)=0} + \underbrace{\sum_{j=k}^k p(s_j)u(f(s_j))}_{=p(s_k)u(f(s_k))} \\
&\quad + \underbrace{\sum_{j=k+1}^n p(s_j)u(\kappa_{\underline{x}}(s_j))}_{=\sum_{j=k+1}^n p(s_j)(0)=0} - \underbrace{\sum_{j=k}^n p(s_j)u(\kappa_{\underline{x}}(s_j))}_{=\sum_{j=k}^n p(s_j)(0)=0} \\
&= p(s_k)u(f(s_k)), \tag{1}
\end{aligned}$$

we can write

$$V(f) - V(\kappa_{\underline{x}}) = \sum_{k=1}^n p(s_k)u(f(s_k)).$$

4.4 Bounds of Telescoping Differences

We're interested in bounding each telescoping difference:

$$\Delta_U(k) := U(f^{(k)}) - U(f^{(k-1)}) \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta_V(k) := V(f^{(k)}) - V(f^{(k-1)}).$$

By construction of $f^{(k)}$ and Axiom 7 (λ -L. continuity),

$$|\Delta_U(k)| = \left| U(f^{(k)}) - U(f^{(k-1)}) \right| \leq \lambda \max_{x,y \in S} \{ |u(f(x)) - u(g(y))| \} \leq \lambda M. \tag{2}$$

The last inequality comes from noticing, for all $x, y \in S$, $u(\kappa_{\underline{x}}) \leq u(f(x))$, $u(g(x)) \leq u(\kappa_{\bar{x}})$. As a consequence,

$$|u(f(x)) - u(g(y))| < |u(\kappa_{\bar{x}}) - u(\kappa_{\underline{x}})| = |M - 0| = M.$$

For $\Delta_V(k)$, we can use λ -Lipschitz continuity again. Recall Equation 1.

$$\begin{aligned}
|\Delta_V(k)| &= |p(s_k)u(f(s_k))| = \left| \frac{U(\delta_{s_k})}{M} u(f(s_k)) \right| \\
&\leq \left| \frac{U(\delta_{s_k})}{M} \max_{s \in S} \{ u(f(s)) \} \right| \leq \left| \frac{U(\delta_{s_k})}{M} M \right| = |U(\delta_{s_k})| \\
&= |U(\delta_{s_k}) - U(\kappa_{\underline{x}})| \leq \lambda \max_{x,y \in S} \{ |u(\delta_{s_k}(s)) - u(\kappa_{\underline{x}}(s))| \} \\
&= \lambda \max_{x,y \in S} \{ |(u(\delta_{s_k}(s)) - 0)| \} \\
&\leq \lambda M. \tag{3}
\end{aligned}$$

4.5 Bounding Expected Utility

We can now chain together the telescoping differences to yield the representation theorem inequality (2). By the triangle inequality,

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \sum_{k=1}^n (U(f^{(k)}) - U(f^{(k-1)})) - \sum_{k=1}^n p(s_k)u(f(s_k)) \right| &\leq \sum_{k=1}^n |U(f^{(k)}) - U(f^{(k-1)}) - p(s_k)u(f(s_k))| \\ &\leq \sum_{k=1}^n |U(f^{(k)}) - U(f^{(k-1)})| + \sum_{k=1}^n |p(s_k)u(f(s_k))| \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^n |\Delta_U(k)| + \sum_{k=1}^n |\Delta_V(k)|. \end{aligned}$$

By equations 2 and 3, $\Delta_U(k), \Delta_V(k) \leq \lambda M$ for all natural $k \leq n$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} |U(f) - V(f)| &= \left| \sum_{k=1}^n (U(f^{(k)}) - U(f^{(k-1)})) - \sum_{k=1}^n p(s_k)u(f(s_k)) \right| \\ &\leq \sum_{k=1}^n |\Delta_U(k)| + \sum_{k=1}^n |\Delta_V(k)| \leq \sum_{k=1}^n (\lambda M) + \sum_{k=1}^n (\lambda M) \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^n 2\lambda M \\ &= n2\lambda M. \end{aligned}$$

4.6 Non-Negativity and Normalisation

In order for p to be an almost-finite additive probability measure, we will prove the following three claims.

1. Non-negativity: for any event $E \subseteq S$,

$$p(E) \geq 0.$$

2. Normalisation:

$$p(S) = 1.$$

3. Almost-finite additivity: let $E, F \subseteq S$ be disjoint. Then

$$|p(E \cup F) - p(F) - p(E)| \leq (|E| + |F|)\lambda.$$

Let $E, F \subseteq S$ be events with $E \cap F = \emptyset$. Moreover, represent

$$E = \{\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \dots, \epsilon_v\} \quad \text{and} \quad F = \{\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_\mu\}.$$

For (1), we have

$$p(E) = \frac{U(\delta_E)}{M} \geq 0,$$

since $U(\delta_E) \geq 0$ and $M > 0$. For (2), we know

$$\delta_S(s) = \begin{cases} \bar{x} & s \in S \\ \underline{x} & s \notin S. \end{cases}$$

Since any event must always be in S , $\delta_S = \kappa_{\bar{x}}$. Thus,

$$p(S) = \frac{U(\delta_S)}{M} = \frac{U(\kappa_{\bar{x}})}{M} = \frac{M}{M} = 1.$$

4.7 Almost-Finite Additivity

For (3), we proceed similarly to the previous sections. Define, for all $0 \leq k \leq v$,

$$E^{(0)} := \emptyset, \quad E^{(k)} := \bigcup_{j=1}^k \epsilon_j \quad \text{and} \quad E^{(v)} := E.$$

Consider the difference

$$\Delta_{E,F}(k) := p(E^{(k)} \cup F) - p(E^{(k-1)} \cup F).$$

By λ -Lipschitz continuity (7),

$$\begin{aligned} |\Delta_{E,F}(k)| &= \left| \frac{U(\delta_{E^{(k)} \cup F})}{M} - \frac{U(\delta_{E^{(k-1)} \cup F})}{M} \right| = \left| \frac{U(\delta_{E^{(k)} \cup F}) - U(\delta_{E^{(k-1)} \cup F})}{M} \right| \\ &\leq \left| \frac{\lambda \max_{x,y \in S} \{u(\delta_{E^{(k)} \cup F}(x)) - u(\delta_{E^{(k-1)} \cup F}(y))\}}{M} \right| \leq \left| \frac{\lambda M}{M} \right| \\ &= \lambda. \end{aligned}$$

By the triangle inequality and the previous equation:

$$|p(E \cup F) - p(F)| = \left| \sum_{k=1}^v (p(E^{(k)} \cup F) - p(E^{(k-1)} \cup F)) \right| = \left| \sum_{k=1}^v \Delta_{E,F}(k) \right| \leq \sum_{k=1}^v \lambda \leq \sum_{k=1}^v |\lambda| = v\lambda. \quad (4)$$

Define $F^{(k)}$ for $1 \leq k \leq \mu$ similarly. Likewise we have

$$|\Delta_{F,E}(k)| := \left| p(F^{(k)} \cup E) - p(F^{(k-1)} \cup E) \right| \leq \lambda.$$

Therefore,

$$|p(E \cup F) - p(E)| \leq \mu\lambda. \quad (5)$$

Combining Equations 4 and 5,

$$|p(E \cup F) - p(F) - p(E)| \leq |p(E \cup F) - p(F)| + |p(E \cup F) - p(E)| \leq (v + \mu)\lambda.$$

We have now proven that p is a almost-finite additive probability measure and V can be constructed. Thus, our proof is complete. \square

4.8 Future Work

I propose the bounds can be tightened since the bounding approach we used was quite conservative. Thus I believe that we may reduce it until

$$|V(f) - U(f)| \leq \lambda n M \quad \text{and} \quad |p(E \cup F) - p(E) - p(F)| \leq \lambda \max\{v, \mu\}.$$

5 Philosophical Implications and Justification

Imposing λ -Lipschitz continuity means we cannot have “discontinuous” reactions, where changing the payoff at a single state makes our utility jump from very bad to very good. Instead, any change in utility is bounded linearly. In other words, minor changes in consequence cannot be majorly amplified—this supports the idea that similar decisions are not valued in drastically different ways. In real life, many decisions adhere to λ -Lipschitz continuity. The additional benefit of λ -Lipschitz continuity is that we may scale λ to be arbitrary large (reasonably up to 1), allowing a “maximal-sized utility jump” to be specified. By restoring the representation theorem up to a degree of error, we’re able to reap the benefits of an approach which maximising expected utility. Unfortunately, “up to a degree” means we lose a bit of precision in the model.

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References

- [1] Maurice Allais. “Le Comportement de l’Homme Rationnel Devant Le Risque: Critique Des Postulats et Axiomes de l’École Américaine”. In: *Econometrica* 21.4 (1953), pp. 503–546. DOI: [10.2307/1907921](https://doi.org/10.2307/1907921).
- [2] Daniel Bernoulli. “Specimen Theoriae Novae de Mensura Sortis”. In: *Commentarii Academiae Scientiarum Imperialis Petropolitanae* 5 (1738).
- [3] Michael Birnbaum. “Tests of branch splitting and branch-splitting independence in Allais paradoxes with positive and mixed consequences”. In: *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes* 102 (2007), pp. 154–173. DOI: [10.1016/j.obhdp.2006.04.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.obhdp.2006.04.004).
- [4] Christiaan Huygens. *De Ratiociniis in Ludo Aleae*. Original treatise on probability. 1657.
- [5] John von Neumann and Oskar Morgenstern. *Theory of Games and Economic Behavior*. Princeton University Press, 1944.
- [6] Blaise Pascal and Pierre Fermat. *Correspondence on the Problem of Points*. Manuscript correspondence. 1654.
- [7] Grant A. Pignatiello et al. “Decision fatigue: A conceptual analysis”. In: *Journal of Health Psychology* 25.1 (2020), pp. 123–135. DOI: [10.1177/1359105318763510](https://doi.org/10.1177/1359105318763510).
- [8] Leonard J. Savage. *The Foundations of Statistics*. John Wiley & Sons, 1954.
- [9] Jim Sollisch. *The Cure for Decision Fatigue*. Wall Street Journal. Accessed 19 July 2025. June 2016. URL: <https://www.wsj.com/articles/the-cure-for-decision-fatigue-1465596928>.
- [10] Amos Tversky and Eldar Shafir. “Choice under Conflict: The Dynamics of Deferred Decision”. In: *Psychological Science* 3.6 (1992), pp. 358–361. DOI: [10.1111/j.1467-9280.1992.tb00047.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9280.1992.tb00047.x).